

Deep Learning-Based Mapping of Woody Floral Resources for Wild Bee Habitat Modelling

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Abstract

The conservation of early-spring wild bees depends on the availability of (woody) floral resources, yet Species Distribution Models (SDMs) often lack detailed data on these biotic interactions. This study addresses this gap by using deep learning to map floral resources and integrating them into SDMs to assess habitat suitability. Using high-resolution airborne imagery of Flanders, Belgium, a trained a deep learning model was trained to segment *Salix* spp. and white flowering trees and shrubs. The models achieved F1-scores of 82.0% and 78.8%, respectively. The segmentation results of the models were converted into floral density maps and integrated into SDMs for early-spring *Andrena* species. Partial dependence profiles revealed a logistic relationship, indicating that habitat suitability rises with floral density until a threshold is reached. These results demonstrate that remote sensing-derived biotic variables can successfully scale fine-scale interactions to regional assessments, providing a tool for identifying resource gaps and prioritizing conservation efforts.

Keywords: Airborne Imagery, Species Distribution Model, Wild Bee Species

1. Introduction

The diversity and availability of floral resources in the landscape surrounding wild bees' nests during their active season is critical to their conservation (Potts et al., 2016; Timberlake et al., 2019). In the Northern Hemisphere, many early-spring species rely on early-flowering trees and shrubs, such as *Prunus* spp. and *Salix* spp. (Barnsley et al., 2022; Neyns et al., 2025). Effective conservation actions therefore require spatial assessments that identify potential resource gaps and analyze their impact on pollinator habitat suitability.

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A commonly used tool for understanding drivers of habitat suitability are species distribution models (SDMs), which correlate geographic occurrence with environmental data. While SDMs traditionally include abiotic variables to describe the environment (e.g. climate and topography), recent studies have increasingly included biotic interactions, such as plant-pollinator interactions, as predictors (Moens et al., 2024). Current approaches for including plant-pollinator interactions primarily rely on measures of flowering plant presence or species diversity. However, these metrics inadequately capture the resource constraints experienced by pollinators. Incorporating floral resource densities should therefore improve our understanding of how resource gaps affect habitat suitability.

While remote sensing has shown potential for floral resource mapping at various scales (Barnsley et al., 2022; Neyns et al., 2025; Pan et al., 2025), there remains little research on the use of remote sensing-derived floral resource maps to understand how their availability affects habitat suitability of wild bees. Therefore, this research aims to 1) apply a geospatial deep learning model to map floral resources availability from trees and shrubs using airborne imagery, and 2) use the resulting maps in SDMs to understand how floral resource availability affects habitat suitability for early-spring bees.

2. Data and Methods

A deep learning-based geospatial segmentation workflow was applied to airborne imagery to map woody floral resources in Flanders (northern Belgium). A multi-year composite mosaic of airborne imagery was used with a spatial resolution of 0.25m, covering the entire region for the period between 2017 and 2023. Through an expert-based visual analysis, specific temporal windows were identified for the target species: willow (*Salix* spp.) was primarily captured in imagery from mid-March to early April, while white flowering species (e.g. blackthorn, *Prunus spinosa*) were most discernable in April imagery.

The geospatial segmentation model used an InceptionResNetV2-U-Net architecture, implemented using the orthoseg software (Roggemans, 2025). Training data for this model were manually delineated using QGIS and Google Street View using local expert knowledge. Two separate models, one for willow, one for white flowering species, were trained using a categorical cross-entropy (CCE) loss function and the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 10⁻⁴ and a batch size of 6. To prevent overfitting, early stopping was applied based on the Jaccard index with a patience of 100 epochs. The trained models were applied to the entire study area image by image and automatically converted to vector layers in the orthoseg software. An object-based accuracy assessment was carried out on the resulting vector layers at independent test sites, and F1-scores were calculated. The workflow is presented in *Figure 1*.

The resulting vector layers were converted into floral density maps and were integrated into SDMs built using Random Forest (RF) and Boosted Trees (BT), implemented with the tidysdm package in R 4.4.3 (Leonardi et al., 2024). Abiotic predictors included in the models were soil texture, topography and land cover at a 200x200m resolution. Nine bee species were selected from the *Andrena* genus based on their activity in early-spring and generalist diet (polylectic). The modelled species are: *Andrena chrysoceles*, *Andrena cineraria*, *Andrena fulva*, *Andrena gravida*, *Andrena haemorrhoa*, *Andrena nigroaenea*, *Andrena nitida*, *Andrena scotica*, and *Andrena tibialis*.

Figure 1. Floral resource mapping workflow using GeoAI.

Bee occurrence data for these species were obtained from Natuurpunt, a nature conservation NGO in Flanders, and comprised opportunistic citizen science observations collected by both professional and amateur observers between 2016 and 2023. Only validated records were retained for modelling and were further filtered to improve data quality. Observations outside the study area or the target period (February–May) were excluded, as were duplicate records and observations with a spatial precision coarser than 100 m. To reduce spatial autocorrelation, the dataset was spatially thinned such that only a single observation was retained per block of 400x400 m. Additionally, a minimum distance of 400m between observations was enforced.

Pseudo-absences were generated by randomly sampling the study area at a 1:1 ratio with the presence data, resulting in an equal number of pseudo-absence and presence records for each species (Barbet-Massin et al., 2012). To account for randomness in pseudo-absence selection, the modelling was repeated ten times for each algorithm using a different pseudo-absence set in each repetition (Sillero et al., 2021). Model performance was assessed using a 10-fold spatial cross-validation with hexagonal blocks, with block size determined separately for each species based on its spatial autocorrelation range (Valavi et al., 2025). Model accuracy was evaluated using the area under the receiver-operating characteristic curve (AUC_{ROC}), the continuous Boyce index (CBI), and the true skill statistic (TSS). Partial dependence profiles were derived from the fitted models using a ceteris-paribus method to evaluate the effect of the floral resource maps. *Figure 2* presents the modelling workflow.

Figure 2. Species distribution modelling workflow

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Floral resource mapping with GeoAI

The mapping of woody floral resources from airborne imagery resulted in F1-scores of 82.0% for willow trees and 78.8% for white flowering vegetation *Figures 3 and 4* present examples of the segmentation results. The delineation of trees and shrubs was generally accurate, but trees and shrubs were occasionally omitted (*Fig. 3a*) and sections of flowering canopies were sometimes undersegmented (*Fig. 3b*). These errors could be due to variations in illumination conditions between images. Although images in the training data were selected to represent variability in illumination conditions, spectral differences between airborne images remain a challenge for accurate segmentation.

3.2 Species distribution modelling

The SDM accuracies for the nine *Andrena* species ranged between 0.72–0.84 for AUC_{ROC}, 0.68–0.74 for CBI and 0.40–0.71 for TSS. *Figure 5* shows that the partial dependence profiles for both biotic variables show similar trends across the nine species, i.e. S-shaped logistic curves. This indicates that once a certain threshold of floral resources is met, other factors, such as nesting site availability or competition, may become more limiting. However, the response curves of the biotic interactions should be interpreted with caution, as error propagation from undersegmentation likely underestimated resource densities. Consequently, the derived thresholds should not be used as management baselines.

Figure 3. Visual comparison of model results on independent test data. (a) Airborne images, truth masks, and prediction masks for the segmentation of willow spp. (b) Airborne images, truth masks and prediction masks for the segmentation of white flowering spp.

Figure 4. Vectorized result of mapped floral resources: willow spp. (blue) and white flowering spp. (red).

Figure 5. Synthesized partial dependence profiles of the two resource density variables willow spp. (left) and white flowering spp. (right). Individual species profiles in grey, the bold lines represent the GAM-smoothed trend and the shaded areas indicating the 0.95 confidence interval. Individual curves for each species are derived from the ensemble of Random Forest (RF) and Boosted Trees (BT) models.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that integrating deep learning-derived floral density maps into SDMs can enhance understanding of how floral resources shape habitat suitability for early-spring bees. By scaling fine-scale biotic interactions to the regional level, this approach provides a framework for identifying resource gaps and informing targeted landscape restoration efforts.

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